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Urolithin A Production by Rare Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Traditional Chinese Qu Starter Cultures

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Abstract

Objectives: To identify food-origin lactic acid bacteria (LAB) capable of converting ellagic acid (EA) to urolithin A (UA) under chemically defined conditions, characterise their biotransformation kinetics, and evaluate preliminary probiotic safety criteria. **Methods:** Fifty-two LAB isolates from traditional Chinese Qu starter cultures were screened for EA-to-UA conversion in MRS broth with 20 μ M pure EA (37°C, 72 h, microaerophilic). UA and EA were quantified by HPLC; UA identity was confirmed by HR-ESI-MS. Producers were identified by 16S rRNA sequencing and subjected to time-course fermentation (0–98 h). Safety assessment covered acid and bile salt tolerance, hemolytic activity, and antibiotic susceptibility. **Findings:** Screening identified two UA-producing strains from 52 isolates (3.8%), both from Qu starters: *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* TCQ1 (99.7% 16S rRNA identity to type strain ATCC 14917^T) and *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* TCQ3 (99.9%). Under defined conditions, TCQ1 produced $7.93 \pm 0.14 \mu$ M UA ($39.65 \pm 0.69\%$ molar conversion), and TCQ3 produced $6.21 \pm 0.31 \mu$ M UA ($31.06 \pm 1.57\%$; $t = 8.68$, $p = 0.001$). Time-course analysis showed strain-specific kinetics: TCQ1 peaked at $6.482 \pm 0.918 \mu$ M at 56 h (44.9% yield) and TCQ3 at $5.575 \pm 0.291 \mu$ M at 72 h (36.1%); both depleted EA to $\approx 100\%$ by 98 h with UA remaining stable thereafter (all post-peak $p > 0.05$). Both strains were γ -hemolytic, retained 10^3 CFU/mL after 3 h at pH 2.0, and maintained >94% survival at 0–0.30% (w/v) bile, satisfying FAO/WHO preselection criteria. **Novelty:** TCQ1 and TCQ3 are the first UA-producing LAB from Chinese Qu starter cultures and represent the first characterisation of EA-to-UA conversion by food-environment LAB isolates using pure EA under defined conditions. TCQ3 is only the second *L. fermentum* strain with confirmed UA-producing capacity. Both strains serve as research platforms for enzymatic pathway investigation and UA-enriched fermented food development.

Keywords: Urolithin A; Lactic Acid Bacteria; Ellagic Acid; Biotransformation; Qu Starter Cultures; Probiotic Screening

1 Introduction

Urolithin A (UA) is a gut microbial metabolite produced from ellagic acid (EA), a polyphenol present in pomegranates, berries, and walnuts⁽¹⁾, and has been reported to activate mitophagy, improve mitochondrial function, and enhance skeletal muscle performance in middle-aged and older adults^{(2), (3), (4)}. UA is currently produced commercially by chemical synthesis involving heavy metal catalysts incompatible with food-grade applications; despite receiving FDA GRAS approval at up to 1,000 mg per serving in 2018⁽⁵⁾, a biological food-grade production route remains unavailable. This health benefit is also metabolite-dependent: approximately 10% of European and Chinese populations belong to urolithin metabolite 0 and lack the gut bacteria required to produce UA endogenously^{(5), (6)}. The gut bacteria responsible for EA-to-UA conversion are predominantly obligate anaerobes, *Gordonibacter* and *Ellagibacter* species initiate the pathway, while *Enterocloster* species complete the final dehydroxylation step⁽⁷⁾, conditions fundamentally incompatible with food-grade production.

Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) represent a promising alternative given their facultative anaerobic physiology, established food safety profiles, and broad fermentative capacity. Several UA-producing LAB have been identified, including *Enterococcus faecium* FUA027⁽⁸⁾, *Streptococcus thermophilus* FUA329⁽⁹⁾, *Lactococcus garvieae* FUA009⁽¹⁰⁾, and *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* FUA033⁽¹¹⁾. Zhang et al.⁽¹²⁾ demonstrated that *L. plantarum* strains from a culture collection produce UA from ellagitannins in pomegranate juice; however, characterisation in a complex polyphenol matrix does not isolate the intrinsic EA-to-UA conversion step. Furthermore, Caballero et al.⁽¹³⁾ demonstrated that food-origin LAB efficiently hydrolyses punicalagin to EA yet produce no detectable urolithins, leaving the EA-to-UA conversion step unresolved among food-derived LAB.

To the best of our knowledge, no study has screened LAB isolated de novo from traditional fermented food environments for EA-to-UA conversion using pure EA under chemically defined conditions. Chinese Qu starters are traditional solid-state fermentation agents matured within a polyphenol-rich grain matrix, providing a chemical environment that may favour enrichment of LAB with polyphenol-metabolising capacity⁽¹⁴⁾. To address this gap, 52 LAB isolates from Qu starter cultures were screened for EA-to-UA conversion using pure EA as substrate under defined conditions; the two positive strains were characterised for biotransformation kinetics and preliminary safety properties, and represent accessible platforms for future investigation of the enzymatic basis of this biotransformation. Food-origin strains capable of producing UA during fermentation could enable the development of UA-enriched fermented foods as a label-clean alternative to chemically synthesised supplements, with particular relevance for metabolite 0 consumers.

2 Methodology

2.1 Materials and Reagents

Ellagic acid (EA, $\geq 98\%$ purity), urolithin A (UA, $\geq 98\%$ purity), and HPLC-grade methanol were purchased from Shanxi Nanda Biological Chemical Co., Ltd. (Shanxi, China). De Man, Rogosa, and Sharpe (MRS) broth and agar, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, $\geq 99\%$ purity), and phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) were obtained from Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd. (Shanghai, China). Hydrochloric acid (HCl, 1 mol/L), ox bile salts, Columbia blood agar (supplemented with 5% defibrinated sheep blood), and antibiotic discs were also supplied by Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd.

2.2 Isolation of Lactic Acid Bacteria

Fermented food samples were collected from markets in Wuxi (Jiangsu, China), representing three categories: dairy products ($n = 25$; yogurt, cheese), plant-based fermentations ($n = 15$; pickles, Qu starters), and meat products ($n = 12$; sausages). Samples were homogenized 1:9 (w/v) in sterile 0.9% NaCl, serially diluted (10^{-1} to 10^{-6}), and spread-plated (0.1 mL) onto MRS agar (pH 6.2) containing cycloheximide (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) to suppress fungal growth. Plates were incubated anaerobically at 37°C for 48 h using a GasPakTM jar system (BD Diagnostics), which generates 85% N₂, 10% CO₂, and 5% H₂; anaerobiosis was confirmed using resazurin redox indicator strips⁽¹⁵⁾. Uninoculated plates served as contamination controls. Morphologically distinct colonies were purified through three successive streaking passages, and purity was verified by uniform colony morphology. Gram staining, catalase negativity, and microscopic morphology confirmed 52 LAB isolates, which were stored at -80°C in MRS broth with 20% (v/v) glycerol.

2.3 16S rRNA Identification

Isolates exhibiting confirmed bioconversion activity were identified by 16S rRNA gene sequencing. Genomic DNA was extracted using the TSINGKE Bacterial DNA Extraction Kit (TSINGKE Biotechnology, Beijing, China) per the manufacturer's instructions. The 16S rRNA gene (1,500 bp) was amplified using primers 27F (5'-AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG-3')

and 1492R (5'-GGTTACCTTGTTACGACTT-3'). PCR reactions (50 μ L) contained 25 μ L TSINGKE 2 \times T8 High-Fidelity Master Mix, 2 μ L of each primer (10 μ M), 2 μ L template DNA, and 19 μ L nuclease-free water. Thermal cycling conditions were: 98°C for 2 min; 35 cycles of 98°C/10 s, 55°C/10 s, 72°C/28 s; final extension at 72°C for 5 min. PCR products were verified by agarose gel electrophoresis, purified, and Sanger-sequenced by TSINGKE Biotechnology. Forward and reverse reads were assembled and quality-trimmed using ContigExpress; consensus sequences were deposited in NCBI GenBank (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nucleotide/>). Species identification used BLASTn (v2.13) against the NCBI nt database, with $\geq 99\%$ identity to a validly published type strain defining species assignment. Sequences were aligned with closely related type strains using ClustalW in MEGA 12. A maximum likelihood tree was constructed under the General Time Reversible model with gamma-distributed rate variation and invariant sites (GTR+G+I; five discrete gamma categories), selected as the best-fit model by the Bayesian Information Criterion. Branch support was assessed using 1,000 standard bootstrap replicates with Nearest-Neighbour-Interchange (NNI) heuristic search. *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* JCM6124 served as the outgroup.

2.4 Bioconversion Assay

Fifty-two LAB isolates were screened for EA-to-UA bioconversion in MRS broth supplemented with 20 μ M EA. EA was dissolved in DMSO (final concentration $\leq 0.1\%$ v/v). Each isolate was pre-cultured overnight in MRS broth at 37°C, standardized to OD₆₀₀ = 0.1 using fresh MRS broth, and inoculated at 1% (v/v) into assay medium. This standardization ensured consistent physiological starting conditions and comparable growth kinetics across all 52 isolates. Four parallel conditions were tested in triplicate per isolate: (i) experimental (MRS + strain + EA); (ii) strain control (MRS + strain); (iii) substrate control (MRS + EA); and (iv) media blank (MRS only). Comparison of conditions (i) versus (ii) confirmed microbial origin of EA transformation, while conditions (iii) and (iv) controlled for spontaneous chemical degradation of EA and background signal, respectively. The tubes were filled almost to capacity to minimize the headspace and then incubated statically at 37°C for 96 h. This reduced-headspace configuration promotes passive oxygen depletion through bacterial respiratory activity, generating microaerophilic conditions suited to the facultative anaerobic physiology of LAB without requiring specialized anaerobic equipment⁽¹⁶⁾.

2.5 Time-Course

The two confirmed UA-producing strains, *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* TCQ1 and *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* TCQ3, were subjected to extended time-course fermentation. A single colony was picked and sub-cultured in 5 mL MRS broth at 37°C for 16–18 h, then standardized to OD₆₀₀ = 0.1 using fresh MRS broth before inoculation at 1% (v/v) into 50 mL MRS broth supplemented with EA, consistent with the conditions described in Section 2.4. The nominal EA concentration was 20 μ M; the actual EA concentration measured by HPLC at t = 0 h was 14.447 ± 1.734 μ M for *L. plantarum* TCQ1 and 15.447 ± 1.609 μ M for *L. fermentum* TCQ3. The deviation from nominal reflects the characteristically low aqueous solubility of EA, which limits complete dissolution even with DMSO as a carrier. All molar conversion yields were calculated using these measured initial concentrations. Culture samples (5 mL) were collected at predetermined time intervals over 98 h: at 0, 12, 24, 36, 48, 56, 72, 86, and 98 h for TCQ1, and at 0, 12, 24, 36, 48, 72, 86, and 98 h for TCQ3 and immediately processed for HPLC analysis as described in Section 2.7. Molar conversion yield and EA consumption were calculated according to Equations 1 and 2:

$$\text{Molar Conversion Yield (\%)} = \frac{[UA]_{\text{produced}}}{[EA]_{t=0}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{EA Consumption (\%)} = \frac{[EA]_{\text{final}}}{[EA]_{t=0}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where [UA]_{produced} is the molar concentration of urolithin A; [EA]_{t=0} is the measured initial EA concentration; and [EA]_{final} is the residual EA concentration at the end of incubation.

2.6 Sample Extraction and Clean-up

Sample extraction was performed according to Iglesias-Aguirre et al.⁽⁷⁾ with minor modifications. Cell-free supernatants were collected from 5 mL culture aliquots by centrifugation at $3,500 \times g$ for 10 min at 4°C, followed by filtration through a 0.45 μ m membrane. Liquid–liquid extraction was performed by adding an equal volume of ethyl acetate acidified with 1.5% (v/v) formic acid; acidification suppresses ionization of ellagic acid and urolithin A, promoting their partition into the organic phase. The mixture was vortexed for 2 min and centrifuged to separate phases. The upper organic layer was evaporated to dryness under vacuum and reconstituted in 250 μ L methanol, then filtered through a 0.22 μ m syringe filter before injection.

2.7 HPLC Analysis

Ellagic acid and urolithin A were quantified by HPLC using an Agilent 1260 Infinity system equipped with a ZORBAX Eclipse Plus C18 column (4.6 × 250 mm, 5 μm) at 30°C, following the method of Zhang et al.^{(9), (12)} with minor modifications. Detection was at 306 nm. Mobile phase A was 0.1% formic acid in water, and mobile phase B was methanol, delivered at 1 mL/min with an injection volume of 10 μL. The gradient of phase B was: 5–18% (0–5 min), 18–28% (5–10 min), 28–50% (10–13 min), 50–90% (13–17 min), 90% hold (17–21 min), 90–5% (21–21.5 min), and re-equilibration at 5% (21.5–25 min). External calibration curves for EA and UA gave $R^2 > 0.998$. Urolithin A identity was further verified by HPLC–ESI–MS using a ZORBAX SB-C18 column (4.6 × 250 mm, 5 μm) at 305 nm over a mass range of 150–2000 Da; identity was confirmed by molecular mass comparison against a pure authentic standard.

2.8 Acid Tolerance and Bile Salt Tolerance Assessment

To evaluate acid tolerance, 10 mL of the overnight culture was centrifuged at $10,000 \times g$ for 10 min. The resulting cell pellet was washed twice with sterile PBS (pH 7.4) and resuspended in MRS broth adjusted to pH 2.0 or 3.0 using 1 mol/L HCl, with unadjusted MRS (pH 6.5) serving as the control. Each strain was inoculated at 2% (v/v) into pH-adjusted media and incubated statically at 37°C under ambient atmosphere. Bacterial survival was assessed by measuring optical density at 600 nm (OD_{600}) at 0, 0.5, 1, 2, and 3 h. Acid tolerance was expressed as log reduction in viable cell count, calculated according to Equation 3:

$$\text{Log Reduction} = \log_{10}(N_0) - \log_{10}(N_t) \quad (3)$$

Where N_0 is the viable cell count (CFU/mL) at 0 h, and N_t is the viable cell count (CFU/mL) at each time point t.

Bile salt tolerance was assessed according to⁽¹⁶⁾ with minor modifications. Following centrifugation and washing with PBS as described above, each strain was inoculated at 2% (v/v) into MRS broth supplemented with 0%, 0.15%, 0.30%, and 0.45% (w/v) bile salts, adjusted to pH 7.0. Cultures were incubated statically at 37°C under ambient atmosphere, and viable cell counts were determined at 0, 2, 4, 6, and 12 h by the pour plate method on MRS agar. Bile salt tolerance was expressed as survival rate (SR%), calculated according to Equation 4:

$$\text{Survival rate (\%)} = \frac{N_{12}}{N_0} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

Where N_{12} is the viable cell count (CFU/mL) at 12 h, and N_0 is the viable cell count (CFU/mL) at 0 h. All measurements were performed in triplicate, and results are reported as mean ± standard deviation (SD).

2.9 Hemolytic Activity Assessment

The hemolytic activity of *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* TCQ1 and *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* TCQ3 was evaluated on Columbia blood agar supplemented with 5% (v/v) defibrinated sheep blood. Both strains were streaked onto the agar surface and incubated aerobically at 37°C for 48 h. Following incubation, colonies were examined visually for the presence or absence of hemolytic zones. Hemolysis was classified as α-hemolysis (partial hemolysis, indicated by greenish discoloration around colonies), β-hemolysis (complete hemolysis, indicated by clear transparent zones), or γ-hemolysis (no visible zone, indicating absence of hemolytic activity), following the criteria described by⁽¹⁷⁾.

2.10 Antibiotic Susceptibility Assessment

The antibiotic susceptibility of *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* TCQ1 and *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* TCQ3 was evaluated using the disk diffusion (Kirby-Bauer) method on MRS agar, following CLSI guidelines and the approach described by⁽¹⁸⁾. Briefly, 100 μL of each strain suspension adjusted to 1.0×10^8 CFU/mL (0.5 McFarland standard) was spread evenly across MRS agar plates. Eleven antibiotic discs were placed onto the inoculated agar surface and gently pressed to ensure full contact: ampicillin (AM, 10 μg), kanamycin (K, 30 μg), streptomycin (S, 10 μg), vancomycin (VA, 30 μg), gentamicin (CN, 30 μg), erythromycin (E, 15 μg), penicillin G (P, 2 μg), neomycin (N, 30 μg), tetracycline (TE, 30 μg), rifampicin (RA, 5 μg), and chloramphenicol (C, 30 μg). Plates were incubated aerobically at 37°C for 48 h, after which inhibition zone diameters were measured in millimeters. Results were interpreted as susceptible (S), intermediate (I), or resistant (R) according to CLSI breakpoint criteria. All experiments were performed in triplicate.

2.11 Statistical Analysis

Data are expressed as mean ± SD (n = 3). Normality was assessed by the Shapiro-Wilk test, and variance homogeneity by Levene’s test. Screening endpoint comparisons (TCQ1 vs TCQ3) used independent samples t-tests, as normality and equal variance assumptions were met. Time-course data were analysed using the Kruskal-Wallis test (normality violated at multiple time points), followed by Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparisons. Acid tolerance, bile tolerance, and antibiotic zone diameters were compared by one-way ANOVA with Tukey’s HSD post hoc test. Hemolytic activity was assessed qualitatively. All analyses were performed in R (v2026.01.1, RStudio, Posit PBC). Significance threshold: p < 0.05.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Results

3.1.1. Taxonomic Identification

L. plantarum TCQ1 and *L. fermentum* TCQ3 were identified by a combination of phenotypic characterisation and 16S rRNA gene phylogenetic analysis. Both strains were Gram-positive, non-spore-forming, non-motile rods with typical LAB colony morphology on MRS agar. In maximum likelihood phylogenetic analysis, TCQ1 clustered within the *L. plantarum* clade (99.7% 16S rRNA identity to type strain ATCC 14917^T; 77% bootstrap at the species node), clearly resolved from the closely related *L. pentosus* (99% bootstrap at that node). TCQ3 grouped with *L. fermentum* reference strains SRCM103290, IMDO130101, and R3 (99.9% identity; 55% species-node bootstrap, 86–98% deeper nodal support). *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* JCM6124^T served as the outgroup and confirmed robust tree topology (Figure 1).

Fig 1. Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* TCQ1 and *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* TCQ3, inferred from 16S rRNA gene sequences (1,500 bp) under the GTR+G+I substitution model (1,000 bootstrap replicates). Both strains are shown in bold. Bootstrap values ≥50% are displayed at nodes. *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* JCM6124^T served as the outgroup. Scale bar: 0.02 substitutions per site.

3.1.2. Screening and Quantification of UA Biotransformation

Of 52 LAB isolates screened, only *L. plantarum* TCQ1 and *L. fermentum* TCQ3, both from Qu starter cultures, converted EA to detectable UA. No UA was detected in substrate controls or in any of the remaining 50 isolates, confirming microbially mediated conversion specific to these two strains (Figure 2A). Under defined conditions (20 μM EA, 37°C, 72 h), TCQ1 produced $7.93 \pm 0.14 \mu\text{M}$ UA (39.65 \pm 0.69% molar conversion), and TCQ3 produced $6.21 \pm 0.31 \mu\text{M}$ UA (31.06 \pm 1.57%). Residual EA was substantially lower for TCQ1 (0.181 \pm 0.035 μM) than TCQ3 (1.035 \pm 0.097 μM), indicating greater substrate consumption by TCQ1. The between-strain difference in UA production was statistically significant ($t = 8.68$, $df = 4$, $p = 0.001$; Figure 2B). UA identity in both culture supernatants was confirmed by HR-ESI-MS against an authentic standard.

Fig 2. Urolithin A (UA) biotransformation from ellagic acid (EA) by *L. plantarum* TCQ1 and *L. fermentum* TCQ3 in EA-supplemented MRS broth (20 μM EA, 37°C, 96 h, static). (A) Representative HPLC chromatograms (306 nm) of fermentation broths alongside EA and UA authentic standards; EA eluted at 9.529 min and UA at 16.733 min. (B) Quantification of residual EA and UA produced after 72 h (mean \pm SD, $n = 3$). No conversion was detected in substrate or media controls. TCQ1 produced significantly more UA than TCQ3 (independent samples t -test; $p = 0.0010$).

3.1.3. Time-Course Analysis

Time-course profiles of EA consumption and UA accumulation by *L. plantarum* TCQ1 and *L. fermentum* TCQ3 are shown in Figure 3A and 3B, respectively. The actual initial EA concentrations, measured by HPLC at $t = 0$ h, were $14.447 \pm 1.734 \mu\text{M}$ for TCQ1 and $15.447 \pm 1.609 \mu\text{M}$ for TCQ3; all conversion yields were calculated relative to these measured values. No UA was detected in either strain at 0 or 12 h, indicating a biotransformation lag phase coinciding with early exponential growth. UA first appeared at 24 h in both strains at trace levels (TCQ1: $0.015 \pm 0.015 \mu\text{M}$; TCQ3: $0.028 \pm 0.049 \mu\text{M}$), though these did not differ significantly from zero (Kruskal-Wallis with Bonferroni post hoc, $p > 0.05$). Appreciable accumulation began from 36 h onwards in both strains.

For *L. plantarum* TCQ1, UA accumulated progressively and peaked at $6.482 \pm 0.918 \mu\text{M}$ at 56 h (molar conversion yield: 44.9%; $p = 0.009$ vs 0 h, Bonferroni-corrected). EA declined from $14.447 \pm 1.734 \mu\text{M}$ to $0.003 \pm 0.006 \mu\text{M}$ by 98 h ($\approx 100\%$ consumption). UA concentrations at 72, 86, and 98 h showed no significant change from the 56 h peak (all $p > 0.05$), indicating that UA was stable and not further metabolised during extended incubation. For *L. fermentum* TCQ3, UA accumulation was slower, reaching its maximum of $5.575 \pm 0.291 \mu\text{M}$ at 72 h (molar conversion yield: 36.1%; $p = 0.000137$ vs 0 h, Bonferroni-corrected) — approximately 16 h later than TCQ1. EA declined from $15.447 \pm 1.609 \mu\text{M}$ to $0.007 \pm 0.012 \mu\text{M}$ by 98 h ($\approx 100\%$ consumption). UA concentrations at 86 and 98 h did not differ significantly from the 72 h peak ($p > 0.05$), confirming post-

peak stability. Both strains therefore achieved near-complete EA depletion and produced UA that remained stable through 98 h, though TCQ1 reached its peak earlier (56 h vs 72 h) and at a higher concentration.

Fig 3. Time-course profiles of EA consumption (closed symbols) and UA accumulation (open symbols) by (A) *L. plantarum* TCQ1 and (B) *L. fermentum* TCQ3 in EA-supplemented MRS broth (20 µM EA, 37°C, static, reduced-headspace microaerophilic conditions). Samples were collected at 0, 12, 24, 36, 48, 60, 72, 84, and 96 h. Data: mean ± SD, n = 3 biological replicates. Statistical comparisons between time points were performed by the Kruskal-Wallis test with Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparisons.

3.1.4. Acid and Bile Salt Tolerance

Acid and bile salt tolerance results are shown in Figure 4. Log reductions in viable cell counts increased in a pH- and time-dependent manner. At pH 2.0 over 3 h, both TCQ1 and TCQ3 reached maximum log reductions of approximately 3.2 log CFU/mL, retaining residual populations of approximately 10³ CFU/mL. Log reductions at pH 3.0 were significantly lower than at pH 2.0 at the 2 h and 3 h time points (p < 0.05, one-way ANOVA with Tukey’s HSD, n = 3; Figure 4A). Both strains maintained survival rates exceeding 94% at 0–0.30% (w/v) ox bile over 12 h. At the supra-physiological concentration of 0.45% (w/v), survival declined to 74.9% (TCQ1) and 74.8% (TCQ3). Survival rates differed significantly across bile concentrations (p < 0.05, one-way ANOVA with Tukey’s HSD, n = 3; Figure 4B).

3.1.5. Hemolytic Activity

Both *L. plantarum* TCQ1 and *L. fermentum* TCQ3 displayed γ-hemolysis on Columbia blood agar supplemented with 5% defibrinated sheep blood after 48 h at 37°C (Figure 5). No clearing zones (β-hemolysis) or greenish discoloration (α-hemolysis) were observed around colonies of either strain.

3.1.6. Antibiotic Susceptibility

Antibiotic susceptibility profiles are shown in Figure 6. Both strains were susceptible to erythromycin (E15), gentamicin (CN30), and chloramphenicol (C30), with inhibition zone diameters of 20–26 mm. Intermediate susceptibility was recorded for ampicillin (AM10), penicillin G (P2), tetracycline (TE30), and rifampicin (RA5), with inhibition zones of 13–16 mm. Both strains were resistant to kanamycin (K30), streptomycin (S10), vancomycin (VA30), and neomycin (N30), with inhibition zones of 6–9 mm. *L. plantarum* TCQ1 showed marginally larger inhibition zones than *L. fermentum* TCQ3 across several antibiotics. All results were interpreted according to CLSI breakpoint criteria.

3.2 Discussion

In the present study, *L. plantarum* TCQ1 and *L. fermentum* TCQ3, both isolated from traditional Chinese Qu starter cultures, were confirmed as capable of converting EA to UA in monoculture under defined laboratory conditions, directly addressing the objective of identifying food-origin LAB with autonomous EA-to-UA conversion capacity. TCQ1 reached peak UA

Fig 4. Gastrointestinal tolerance of *L. plantarum* TCQ1 and *L. fermentum* TCQ3. (A) Log reduction in viable cell counts (CFU/mL) following 3 h static exposure at pH 2 and pH 3.0 (MRS adjusted with 1 mol/L HCl; unadjusted MRS pH 6.5 as control; 37°C, ambient atmosphere). (B) Survival rate (SR%) following 12 h static exposure to ox bile (Oxgall; 0–0.45% w/v) at 37°C. Data: mean ± SD (n = 3). Different letters indicate significant differences between bile concentrations (one-way ANOVA, Tukey’s HSD, p < 0.05).

Fig 5. Hemolytic phenotype of *L. plantarum* TCQ1 (right) and *L. fermentum* TCQ3 (left) on Columbia blood agar supplemented with 5% defibrinated sheep blood, after 48 h incubation at 37°C. The absence of clearing zones (β -hemolysis) or greenish discoloration (α -hemolysis) around colonies confirms γ -hemolysis (no hemolytic activity) for both strains, consistent with FAO/WHO probiotic safety criteria.

Fig 6. Antibiotic susceptibility profiles of *L. plantarum* TCQ1 and *L. fermentum* TCQ3 were assessed by the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method on MRS agar (37°C, 48 h). Inhibition zone diameters (mm) are shown for eleven antibiotics. Bars: mean \pm SD (n = 3). Susceptibility categories (susceptible/intermediate/resistant) were assigned according to CLSI breakpoint criteria.

accumulation of $6.482 \pm 0.918 \mu\text{M}$ at 56 h (44.9% molar yield), and TCQ3 reached $5.575 \pm 0.291 \mu\text{M}$ at 72 h (36.1% molar yield), with near-complete EA depletion ($\approx 100\%$) confirmed in both strains by 98 h.

The molar yields reported here are comparable to those documented for other food-origin UA-producing LAB under defined-medium conditions. Liu et al.⁽⁹⁾ reported UA production by *Streptococcus thermophilus* FUA329, and Mi et al.⁽¹⁰⁾ characterised *Lactococcus garvieae* FUA009, both from human milk and intestinal sources, respectively. In the present study, TCQ1 and TCQ3 achieved comparable yields from Qu-origin isolates, extending the ecological range of food-origin UA-producing LAB beyond dairy and intestinal niches^{(19), (20)}. Wang et al.⁽²¹⁾ identified a lactonase gene (*lac1563*) responsible for UA production in *L. fermentum* FUA033; whether a homologous gene is present in TCQ3 was not investigated and represents a priority for future genomic analysis.

A key methodological distinction of the present study is the use of pure EA in a defined MRS medium. Zhang et al.⁽¹²⁾ and Wu et al.⁽¹¹⁾ characterised UA production by *L. fermentum* FUA033 in complex food matrices, including strawberry juice, where multiple polyphenols introduce confounding variables that obscure intrinsic conversion capacity. The defined-medium approach used here isolates the EA-to-UA step and provides reproducible, quantitative baseline data, a prerequisite for process optimisation and future scale-up.

The present findings extend the work of Caballero et al.⁽¹³⁾, who demonstrated that 30 food-origin LAB strains efficiently hydrolyse punicalagin to EA but produce no detectable urolithins. Their study established that food-origin LAB can engage the upstream step of the conversion pathway; however, the assay design, using punicalagin in a complex substrate rather than pure EA, did not isolate the EA-to-UA conversion step and therefore could not determine whether these strains possess the capacity to complete it. The present study was designed to address this gap directly by presenting pure EA as a substrate to LAB isolates from a broad panel of food sources. Under these conditions, TCQ1 and TCQ3 completed the conversion. This outcome suggests that EA-to-UA conversion capacity may be present among food-origin LAB but had remained undetected because no prior study had used pure EA with isolates from polyphenol-rich fermentation sources such as Qu.

Both strains showed a biotransformation lag phase of 0–24 h, during which EA declined but UA remained undetectable. Appreciable UA accumulation began from 36 h, coinciding with the onset of the stationary phase, consistent with the growth-phase dependence reported for *S. thermophilus* FUA329⁽⁹⁾. The lag in UA appearance most likely reflects the sequential accumulation and turnover of intermediate urolithins that were not quantified in this assay. Alternatively, the delay may reflect the time required for induction or upregulation of the conversion machinery under substrate-rich, nutrient-limited conditions, a regulatory response rather than an enzymatic bottleneck. These interpretations are not mutually exclusive, and distinguishing

between them would require intermediate metabolite profiling combined with transcriptomic analysis during the 24–56 h window. Following peak accumulation, UA concentrations in both strains remained statistically unchanged through 98 h (all consecutive post-peak comparisons $p > 0.05$, Bonferroni-corrected), indicating that neither strain further metabolises UA under the assay conditions. This end-product stability is a practically relevant attribute; it suggests that the bioactive compound would be preserved rather than degraded during fermentation, supporting the potential use of these strains in functional food or probiotic formulations designed to deliver UA.

The isolation of both strains from the Qu starter cultures is consistent with the ecological rationale developed in this study. Hua et al. (22) noted recently that no GRAS-status LAB with confirmed UA-producing capacity had been characterised before this work, identifying food-origin screening as a priority. Both TCQ1 and TCQ3 carry established food-origin provenance and are phylogenetically placed within species with GRAS/QPS recognition, distinguishing them from the fecal-origin strains that characterise most previously described UA producers (23). *L. fermentum* TCQ3 represents only the second *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* strain with confirmed UA-producing capacity, following the fecal-origin FUA033 (21); its independent isolation from a distinct ecological niche suggests this trait may be more broadly distributed across *L. fermentum* ecological variants than currently recognised. These findings suggest that systematic screening of existing *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* and *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* culture collections, particularly those from traditional Asian fermented foods where polyphenol-rich substrates are common, may reveal additional UA-producing strains and map the true distribution of this rare metabolic trait (19), (20).

As a preliminary assessment of applied potential, four standard probiotic preselection parameters were evaluated: acid tolerance, bile salt tolerance, hemolytic activity, and antibiotic susceptibility. These constitute the minimum screening battery recommended by FAO/WHO guidelines and widely applied in the LAB literature as a first-pass elimination filter (18), (24). Strains that fail any single criterion do not warrant the resource investment of deeper validation. Both TCQ1 and TCQ3 satisfied all four criteria: they retained viable populations of approximately 10^3 CFU/mL after 3 h at pH 2.0, maintained survival rates exceeding 94% at physiologically relevant bile concentrations of up to 0.30% (w/v), were classified as γ -hemolytic, and displayed antibiotic resistance patterns consistent with intrinsic, non-transferable profiles documented for *Lactiplantibacillus* and *Limosilactobacillus* species (17). These results do not establish probiotic status; comprehensive evaluation, including gastrointestinal adhesion, immunomodulatory activity, biogenic amine screening, and genome-based safety assessment, would be required before either strain could be considered a probiotic candidate (16), (18). The present data establish that TCQ1 and TCQ3 pass the initial filter and justify inclusion in such programmes.

Several limitations define clear directions for future work. The genetic and enzymatic basis of UA production in TCQ1 and TCQ3 was not investigated; comparative genomic and transcriptomic analyses during the active conversion phase (36–72 h) would identify the responsible genes and regulatory networks. Intermediate urolithins were not monitored, precluding a complete mass-balance analysis; targeted LC-MS/MS profiling would address this. Strain stability under repeated subculturing and performance in complex food matrices or gut simulation models remains to be established. Whether oral administration of either strain enhances circulating UA levels in metatype 0 individuals, those who cannot produce UA endogenously, represents the most translatable question for future in vivo investigation.

4 Conclusions

This study has identified two lactic acid bacteria from traditional Chinese Qu starter cultures, *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* TCQ1 and *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* TCQ3, capable of converting ellagic acid to urolithin A in monoculture under chemically defined conditions. TCQ1 produced a molar conversion yield of 44.9% with a peak at 56 h, and TCQ3 produced 36.1% with a peak at 72 h; both strains achieved near-complete EA depletion by 98 h with UA concentrations remaining stable thereafter. Characterisation in a pure EA-defined medium isolates the intrinsic EA-to-UA conversion step and provides a reproducible baseline not previously available from complex matrix studies. To the best of our knowledge, TCQ1 and TCQ3 are the first UA-producing LAB isolated from Qu starter cultures; TCQ3 represents only the second *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* strain with confirmed UA-producing capacity, following the fecal-origin FUA033, and its isolation from a distinct ecological niche extends the known distribution of this rare metabolic trait. Both strains satisfied FAO/WHO minimum preselection criteria for acid tolerance, bile salt tolerance, hemolytic safety, and antibiotic susceptibility, though this does not constitute probiotic validation.

TCQ1 and TCQ3 thus represent accessible, food-origin research platforms with clearly documented EA-to-UA conversion capacity. Their food-grade provenance, facultative physiology, and defined-medium characterisation could facilitate future comparative genomic and transcriptomic investigation of the enzymatic basis of UA biosynthesis. In applied terms, food-origin LAB strains with confirmed UA-producing capacity could support the development of UA-enriched fermented foods as biologically sourced alternatives to chemically synthesised supplements, an outcome of particular relevance for metatype 0

individuals who cannot produce UA endogenously. In vivo validation of this potential represents the most translatable direction for future work.

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